

Evaluating mRNA COVID-19 Vaccine safety and Identifying Potential Causes of Its Side Effects

Shichun Zhang – Carlucci American International School of Lisbon
Lisbon, Portugal

Email: shichunzhang040910@gmail.com

Introduction & Background

mRNA vaccine is one of the newest vaccines used during the pandemic. Due to its novelty, there is limited research on its side effects. It is hard to make a reasonable correlation between some adverse side effects and their causes. These side effects greatly concern the public, which eventually causes vaccine hesitancy and lower vaccine acceptance. This project aims to investigate the side effects of the COVID-19 mRNA vaccine and compare that with the conventional vaccine through literature review and propose potential causes of those side effects. The hypothesis is that the reported side effects of the mRNA COVID vaccine are similar to that of conventional attenuated influenza vaccines.

Table 1. COVID-19 Vaccine Acceptance Rate by Country

Figure 1. Schematic Structure of SARS-CoV-2 Virus

Methods

This project is purely based on a literature review and uses pre-existent data. We collected data on severe and normal side effects of influenza and Pfizer mRNA vaccine and attempted to correlate them. Pfizer vaccine data are taken from the CDC site, and influenza vaccine taken from the WHO Influenza vaccine information sheet.

Results

Table 2. Comparison of Common and Severe Side Effects in Pfizer mRNA Vaccine and Attenuated Virus Vaccine

5 in 1 million had anaphylaxis with Pfizer vaccine
0.7 in 1 million had anaphylaxis with influenza vaccine

Potential Cause of Anaphylaxis:

- Hypersensitivity of Polyethylene glycol (PEG)
- Supported by Literature: Recipients who are allergic to PEG displays symptoms of Anaphylaxis when receiving mRNA vaccine.

Acknowledgement

This project is supported by Rapidamic Lab.

mRNA Vaccine

Attenuated Virus Vaccine

Figure 2. Schematic Structure of mRNA Vaccine and Attenuated Virus Vaccine

Discussion & Conclusion

Percentage of Pfizer recipients with systematic reactions could be close to or less than that in the conventional vaccine group. Severe side effects such as anaphylaxis occurred more among Pfizer recipients. Analysis on common side effects shows that it does prove the hypothesis. Anaphylaxis should be further investigated due to a huge difference in its occurring rates.

Future Research

Investigation of causes of adverse effects that includes delivery system components like PEG and potential toxic effects of any non-native nucleotides.

References

- CDC Database
- Pardi, N. et al. Nat Rev Drug Discov 17, 261–279 (2018).
- Nature 580, 576–577
- WHO “Information Sheet Observed Rate of Vaccine Reactions Influenza Vaccine”
- Stone, C. A. et al. The journal of allergy and clinical immunology. In practice, 7(5), 1533–1540.e8.
- Sallam, M. Vaccines 2021, 9, 160.
- Sellaturay, Priya et al. Clinical and experimental allergy : journal of the British Society for Allergy and Clinical Immunology, 51(6), 861–863.